

Smart Captcha Version 1

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Abstract— This is an era of internet. Life without internet is unimaginable. Even in this tough lockdown period internet plays an vital role in our life. Daily activities like online teaching, online banking, online shopping, online bill payments etc. is done through internet. However these activities can be threatened by the attacks called bots which is an automated computer program developed for automatic registration of web services to steal important credential of human data. CAPTCHA (Completely Automated Public Turing Test to Tell C omputers and Human Apart.) distinguishes human users and automated computer program. Captcha offers good security from automatic registration to web services. There are several CAPTCHA's with their strength and weakness. Smart CAPTCHA was proposed in 2019. Smart captcha is a Microsoft multilayer text based captcha combined with an image which can be solved using check box[site smart captcha].Smart Captcha version 1 is an updated version of smart captcha. Smart Captcha version 1 is a combination of text based captcha and image based captcha where image is displayed as jigsaw puzzle. Humans can easily solve this captcha within ten seconds but it is difficult for bots to solve this captcha.

Index Terms—BOTS, CAPTCHA, Image Captcha, Microsoft multi-layer Captcha, Text-based Captcha, Smart Captcha version 1, Jigsaw puzzle.

Introduction

CAPTCHA(Completely Automated Public Turing Test to Tell Computers and Human Apart.) is a Turing test that distinguishes human from computer. Captcha's are security check which averts hackers/spammers to get important user credentials by automatic registration to web services. Captcha prevents the bots to perform the malicious activities like spams in emails, misusing free web services, comments spamming in blogs, attacks in password system, worms, virus to hack the system through email and many fraudulent activities. Captcha should be very simple for human to solve and difficult for bots to solve. Captcha should have following characteristics [25]

1. Simple for human to solve
2. Difficult for bots to solve
3. Front end complexity should be as low as possible without compromising its security aspects.
4. Captcha should be easily generated
5. Captcha should be easily solved in few seconds or microseconds by humans.

Following are few Captcha available in the market.

reCAPTCHA[7] – Most simple Captcha developed by Google search engine which simply asks user to tick on the check box ' I M NOT ROBOT'

Figure 1 reCAPTCHA

Microsoft Two layer Captcha – Microsoft deployed two layer captcha in 2015 in which all characters were connected with each other from left-to-right, top-to-bottom

Figure 2 Microsoft two layer captcha

Image Based Captcha using Jigsaw Puzzle – In this captcha the pieces of images are dislocated. The user should still identify the image. Human can solve this captcha very easily where as it is difficult for bots to solve this captcha.

Figure 3 Image Based Captcha using Jigsaw Puzzle

Smart Captcha – Smart Captcha is a multilayer text based captcha combined with an image which can be solved using checkbox[25].

Figure 4 – Smart Captcha

In this paper section 2 discusses survey of existing captcha, section 3 discusses the proposed system, section 4 discusses results, section 5 discusses conclusion and future work and finally the references.

REVIEW OF CAPTCHA:

A. reCAPTCHA – reCAPTCHA was created by Luis Von Ahn and was aided by a MacArthur Fellowship in 2007. The main objective to create the recaptcha was save the time require to type the letter of text based captcha with just clicking on checkbox 'I M NOT ROBOT' without compromising the security aspects. reCaptcha was acquired by Google in September 2009. reCaptcha uses an advanced risk analysis engine and adaptive challenge to keep malicious software from engaging in abusive activities on website

B. Gimpy Captcha – Gimpy Captcha is a text based captcha which selects a word or selects random letters distorts them add noise and background and display them. Gimpy captcha was build for YAHOO to keep bots away [30].

Figure 5 – Gimpy Captcha

C. Math Solution – In this type of Captcha simple math problem are displayed like $1 + 2$ or $3 - 2$ which user should solve and submit the answer in text box. The math equation are very simple, quickly solvable and easy to read[28].

Figure 6 – Math Solution Captcha

D. 3D Captcha – In this type of Captcha several 3D words is displayed which is hard for bots and OCR to recognize but can be solved by humans.

Figure 7 – 3D Captcha

E. Microsoft Two Layer Captcha – Microsoft deployed two layer captcha in 2015. In this two layer captcha the sides of each characters were connected together from top to bottom and from left to right.

F. *Picture identification of Captcha* - This captcha provides the user for selecting the correct image that they have asked to identify[28].

Figure 8 – Picture identification Captcha

G. Tic Tac Toe Captcha – This Captcha was designed for fun and involves gamification which ensures that only humans can interact with your website[29].

Figure 9 – Tic Tac Toe Captcha

H. *Sweet Captcha* – This type of Captcha asks the user to match the image instead of entering text of digits in text box[29]

Figure 10 – Sweet Captcha

I. *Drag and Drop Captcha* - In this type of captcha the user is asked to drag and drop specified item into circle. This captcha protects your web page from spammers and bots.

Figure 11 – Drag and Drop Captcha

J. *Image Based Captcha using Jigsaw Puzzle* – This method the entire image is broken into nine segments and the segment are dislocated. The user should place this pieces in correct location to form the entire image and recognize it.

K. *Time Based Captcha* - In Time based captcha the user should solve simple math problems in few seconds. Thus time based captcha distinguishes human from bots because humans can easily solve the simple math problem and submit it while it may take time for bots to solve the captcha.

L. *Smart Captcha* – Smart Captcha is composed of text based multilayer Captcha combined with an image. The user has to recognize the text captcha and image and tick on correct check box. Smart Captcha is a time base captcha which should be solved within 10 seconds which make it more difficult for bots to solve the captcha.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

Smart Captcha Version 1 is the extended version of smart captcha. It is implemented in java. Smart captcha version 1 is composed of text based captcha and image. Text based in smart captcha version 1 is generated using characters, digits and few special symbols. The character ranges is from "A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I, J, K, L, M, N, O, P, Q, S, T, U, V, W, X, Y, Z, a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j, k, l, m, n, o, p, q, r, s, t, u, v,

w, x, y, z" and numbers ranges from "1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9," and special characters range from "@, #, \$, &". These characters, numbers and special characters are selected randomly to generate a text-based captcha. One image is selected randomly from the database, this image is broken into pieces the pieces are dislocated and the image is displayed in scrambled format. The image and text based captcha are combined which creates smart captcha version 1.

Three checkboxes are generated and one among which composes of exact text for text-based captcha and text for the image. If the user ticks the right checkbox then the captcha is solved and if the user ticks on the wrong checkbox the error message is displayed "Wrong Captcha" and new captcha is reloaded. The proposed algorithm is times based, the user has to solve the captcha within 10 seconds else an error message is displayed "Time Out" and new captcha is reloaded [25].

A. *Mathematical Model*

Good Captcha - Captcha Test T which is solved by human with probability 1 as success rate whereas success rate to solve Captcha Test T for bots is negligible or nil.

Definition - Captcha Test T is said to be successful if Captcha Test T be (α, β) is human executable and at α portion of population has success greater than β over T where $(\alpha > \beta)$ and captcha Test T is NIL or negligible for bots

Proof - $C1 \in \{SC \text{ ver } 1\}$ SC ver 1 is smart captcha version 1, C1 is a text captcha

C2 is an image captcha

t1 is the time required to solve text captcha

t2 is time required to analyze image captcha

t3 is the time required to solve image captcha

$t1 + t2 + t3$ is the time required to solve smart captcha by bots

t is the time required to solve the smart captcha version within 10 seconds

- On input x by bot run a captcha test T for C1
 - If captcha test passes that is $T == x$ in time t1 then accept x and halt. Print success captcha solved in t1 seconds
 - If the captcha test does not passes that is $T \neq x$ in time t1 second then reject and load new captcha C1
- On input x1 by bot run a captcha test T1 for C2
 - If captcha test passes that is $T1 == x1$ in time t3 seconds then accept x1 and halt. Print success captcha solved in t3 seconds
 - If the captcha test does not passes that is $T1 \neq x1$ in time t3 second then reject and load new captcha C2

Let $t4 = t1 + t2 + t3$

If bot solves the captcha in t4 seconds where $t4 < 10$ seconds then captcha can be solved by bots else

Smart captcha version 1 are unsolvable by bots in time t if and only if $t4 > t$.

B. Algorithm

Step 1 – Initialize a character string to {'A to Z', 'a to z', '1 to 9', '@', '#', '&', '\$'}

Step 2 – Set maximum length of text-based captcha to 5

Step 3 – Generate each character in the text-based captcha with different color

Step 4 – Add a background to the text-based captcha **Step 5**- Randomly choose any one image from the database

Step 6 – Divide the selected image into smaller image chunks.

Step 7 – Shuffle the smaller image position and rebuild new image which is scrambled image.

Step 8 – Combine it with text-based captcha and generate a new captcha named Smart Captcha version 1 which is a combination of text and image based captcha and scrambled image captcha

Step 9 – Generate a three checkbox randomly which is composed of exact text for text-based captcha and text for the image.

Step 10 - Check whether the user ticks the right checkbox. If the user ticks the right checkbox then the captcha is solved and if the user ticks on the wrong checkbox the error message is displayed "Wrong Captcha" and new captcha is reloaded.

Step 11 – Check whether the user solves the captcha within 10 seconds.

Step 12 if the user is unable to solve the captcha within 10-second display error message "Timeout" and reload new captcha.

RESULTS

Smart Captcha version 1 is implemented in java. Smart captcha version 1 first generates text based captcha which comprises of five characters. Following is the output of text based captcha.

Figure 12 – Textbased Captcha of Smart Captcha ver1

Next, the algorithm selects any one image from the database randomly. In this case, the algorithm has selected the image of a cow

Figure 13 – Image Captcha of Smart Captcha version 1 This selected image is broken to smaller chunks of image

Figure 14 – Image Chunk 1 Figure 15 – Image Chunk 2

16 – Image Chunk 3 Figure 17 – Image Chunk 4

This smaller chunk of image is shuffled and combined to form new scrambled image of cow. Following is the output

Figure 18 Scrambled Image Captcha of Smart Captcha version 1

Now algorithm combines this scrambled image and text-based captcha to form a Smart Captcha and following is the output

Figure 19 Text Captcha and Scrambled Image Captcha combined for Smart Captcha version 1
The final output of our proposed algorithm looks like this

Figure 20 Final Output of smart Captcha version 1

When user ticks on correct option within 10 seconds the smart captcha version 1 is solved.

This captcha was tested with more than 1000 people and around 400 users gave a positive feedback for the proposed captcha. Many user found it easy and were able to solve it in less than ten seconds. Captcha was clear, understandable and easy to solve and hence many user rated it in between 100 to 90 points.

Feed Back Form

1. Is the captcha clear, readable and easy to solve
 Yes No Can't Say
2. Is the captcha understandable
 Yes No Can't Say
3. Does the captcha takes less time to solve
 Yes No Can't Say
4. How will you rate this captcha
 5 4 3
 2 1
5. Any other suggestion/comments

Figure 21 feedback form for smart captcha version 1

Figure 21 illustrates the feedback form for smart captcha version 1. Feedback form is composed of five points where first points ensures clarity of the captcha, because now a days there are many captcha which complicated and unreadable for the human’s too. Second point checks whether the user is understanding the captcha and can solve it. Third point checks the time required for the user to solve the captcha. Now a days there are many captcha that are not solved even in 30 seconds and they simply go in infinite loop blocking our work. Fourth points in the feedback form checks the likeliness of captcha by the user. Fifth point is designed to collect some additional information.

Figure 21 Feedback of Smart Captcha version 1

Figure 21 illustrates the graph for feedback of smart captcha version 1. The graph denotes that when tested more than 400 users rated it for positively. More than 300 users were neutral and more than 200 people rated it negatively.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Our proposed algorithm smart captcha version 1 is clear, readable and can be solved by humans in less than ten seconds and is implemented in Java. Our captcha is composed of two parts text captcha and scrambled image captcha, the user should tick on right checkbox within 10 second which maps text for text-based captcha and text for image-based captcha. The proposed captcha was tested with 1000 users and it was more than 700 user were able to solve the captcha in less than 10seconds.

Future Work

Text-based captcha can be made more complicated by using distortion, rotation and split algorithm which is still easy for a human to recognize in few second but difficult for bots or OCR algorithms to solve in a specified time.

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